

Waste biorefinery technologies for accelerating sustainable energy processes

WIRE COST Action's 6th Working Groups Workshop, Novi Sad 10-11th October 2024

Human Health Aspects in Waste Biorefinery Technologies and Products

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Abstract:

Climate change serves as a powerful catalyst, urging us to reevaluate our relationship with the planet. Its negative impacts are most notably seen in rising CO₂ levels, which drive global temperature increases, as well as the growing waste production. Acknowledging these challenges has sparked the development of biorefinery technologies aimed at producing cleaner energy and sustainable products. Beyond reducing environmental harm, these innovations can indirectly benefit human health and well-being. However, when introducing any product for human use, we must also consider its direct impact on the human body. Although biorefinery technologies generate bio-based products, this doesn't automatically guarantee they are entirely safe for human health. Engineered living materials (ELMs) offer a promising avenue within biorefinery technologies, as they combine biological functions with structural capabilities, potentially enhancing sustainability and reducing waste. However, given their dynamic nature, it is essential to thoroughly evaluate the interaction between these materials and human health to ensure they are safe for direct or indirect human exposure. Therefore, it is crucial to assess their potential influence on health to optimize production processes and ensure truly sustainable products that pose no harm to human health. One simple and effective method to evaluate the safety of these products is cytotoxicity testing. This involves testing the substance or product on human cells *in vitro* and observe their response to it. After exposure, the viability and morphology of the cells are examined to detect any potential toxic effects. As the famous Latin phrase reminds us, "*sola dosis facit venenum*" (the dose makes the poison) - even essential molecules like vitamins can be harmful if consumed in excessive amounts. This highlights the importance of determining the safe dosage for any substance we are exposed to. In the context of biorefinery technologies, understanding the balance between environmental friendliness and human safety is key to developing products that are both sustainable and non-toxic.

Acknowledgments: This publication is based upon work from COST Action WIRE, CA20127, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology). This research was funded by the European Union (ERC, ARCHI-SKIN, #101044468). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Valentina Hribljan holds a Master's degree in Molecular Biology and a PhD in Biomedicine (Neuroscience). During her PhD, she focused on the effects of stem cells on the recovery of neural cells injured by hypoxia-ischemia. From January 2024, she is employed in the Materials Department at InnoRenew CoE, where one of her primary responsibilities is assessing the cytotoxicity of various materials.